

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**DEVELOPMENT OF NEOSOMAL GEL FORMULATIONS OF
PIROXICAM FOR THE TREATMENT OF RELIEVING PAIN
DURING MENSTRUAL CRAMPS****E.SREEJA¹, V.MADHAVI², PJV SAGAR³, P.PARTHIBAN⁴**¹ Department of Pharmaceutics, NOVA College of Pharmaceutical Education and Research, Vijayawada.^{2,4} Asst. Professor, Department Of Pharmaceutics, NOVA College of Pharmaceutical Education and Research, Vijayawada.³ Principal, NOVA College Of Pharmaceutical Education and Research, Vijayawada

Abstract: *Over the past several years, treatment of infectious diseases and immunisation has undergone a revolutionary shift. With the advancement of biotechnology and genetic engineering, not only a large number of disease-specific biologicals have been developed, but also emphasis has been made to effectively deliver these biologicals. Niosomes are vesicles composed of non-ionic surfactants, which are biodegradable, relatively nontoxic, more stable and inexpensive, an alternative to liposomes. The current deepening and widening of interest of niosomes in many scientific disciplines and, particularly its application in medicine. Piroxicam is a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) that exhibits anti-inflammatory, antirheumatoid, arthritis, analgesic, and antipyretic activities in animal models. Piroxicam like other non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs causes side-effects on the gastro-intestinal system and other systems of the body. Because of these side effects the patient compliance may reduce. The best alternative route for administration of PIR is transdermal route.*

Keywords: Piroxicam, Niosomes, Surfactants

Corresponding author:**E.Sreeja,**

Department of Pharmaceutics

NOVA College of Pharmaceutical Education and Research,
Vijayawada.Email id: 9reddysreeja7@gmail.com

Please cite this article in press E.Sreeja et al., *Development of Neosomal Gel Formulations of Piroxicam for the Treatment of Relieving Pain during Menstrual Cramps*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(05).

INTRODUCTION:

Basically there are three route of drug administration oral, topical & parentral. Among that topical i.e. skin provide efficient route for API administration. Stratum corneum in epidermal layer found to be major barrier for penetration of API through or in to the skin.

Topical drug delivery system means delivery of API through or in to the skin for direct treatment of cutaneous disorder or the cutaneous manifestation.

Topical drug delivery systems include a large variety of pharmaceutical dosage form like semisolids, liquid preparation, sprays and solid powders. Most widely used semisolid preparation for topical drug delivery includes gels, creams and ointments.

Fungus infection (Mycoses) is a human infection is broadly of two types. Superficial & deep seated (systemic) superficial infection is by far common & comprises the various types of tinea or ringworm affecting the skin, hair & nails. Superficial mycoses having two types surface infection & cutaneous infection. In cutaneous disorder mostly fungal infection occurs superficially. Novel topical drug delivery systems include niosomes, liposomes, and solid lipid nanoparticles etc. which are highly effective for topical route of drug administration.

Conventional preparation like Ointment, gel, cream, emulsion shows problem of drug penetration as well as API deposition. So to overcome this problem there is need to develop novel formulation act as carrier for better penetration through topical formulations.

Niosomal gels contain nanometric systems embedded in a gel. Nanometric systems have a greater surface area, which renders them highly satisfactory for the application of drug substances promoting a homogeneous drug release. Such structures have been investigated as alternatives to the classical formulations based on chemical skin permeation enhancers. Additionally, the nanostructure systems have nano size so it is easy for application to the skin in dermatological product

In the present study it has been aimed at developing a niosomal drug delivery system of piroxicam by solvent evaporation technique.

The objective of the present study is to enhance the dissolution release profile of piroxicam. This was developed by using, span 80 and cholesterol as a carrier, surfactant, lipid respectively.

List of Materials used for formulation

SI.No	Materials	Supplied by
1	Piroxicam	Gift sample from Dr.Reddy's Laboratories Ltd., Hyd
2	Cholesterol	S.D.Fine Chemicals, Mumbai.
3	Span 60	S.D.Fine Chemicals, Mumbai.
4	Methanol	Merck Specialities Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai.
5	Chloroform	Merck Specialities Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai.
6	carbopol	S.D.Fine Chemicals, Mumbai.

METHODOLOGY:**ANALYTICAL STUDIES:****Construction of standard graph**

For the spectrophotometric analysis stock solutions of piroxicam was prepared by dissolving 10 mg of the drug in 10 ml distilled water to obtain a final concentration of 1 mg/ml. Serial dilutions were made to prepare diverse sample solutions of concentrations ranging from 2–20 μ l/ml. The solutions were analyzed at an absorption maximum of 304 nm against the blank.

Formulation of Niosomes

NIOSOMES were prepared by using slurry method (13). The composition of different proniosomal formulations is represented in (Table 4.3).

In brief, accurately weighed amounts of lipid mixture comprising of span 60 and cholesterol as per formulation ratios were dissolved in 20ml of solvent mixture containing chloroform and methanol (2:1). The resultant solvent solution was transferred into a 250ml round bottom flask. The flask was attached to a rotary flash evaporator (Hei-VAP advantage/561-01300, Heidolph, Germany) and the organic solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure at a temperature of $45\pm 2^{\circ}$ C. The obtained niosomes were stored in a tightly closed container for further evaluation.

Preparation of Gel: Carbopol 934 was taken as polymer for the formation of Gel. 1% Carbopol was chosen for preparing gel. Weighed amount of Carbopol 934 was taken in a dry beaker and to this water was added and kept aside for swelling of carbopol for 3 hours. After complete swelling of carbopol, slowly stir with glass rod and to this add few drops of Tri ethanol amine (TEA) and this turns the preparation into gel. To this gel the prepared NIOSOMES were added.

Fig.1: Schematic representation of Proniosomal formulation of Piroxicam.

Table 1: Formulation of NIOSOMES

Formulation code	Drug (Piroxicam)	Surfactant	Cholesterol	Solvent (2:1)
NG1	20	Sapn 60	100	Chloroform and methanol
NG2	20	Sapn 60	100	Chloroform and methanol
NG3	20	Sapn 60	100	Chloroform and methanol
NG4	20	Sapn 60	50	Chloroform and methanol
NG5	20	Sapn 60	50	Chloroform and methanol

Evaluation

Morphological evaluation of prepared proniosome powders by Scanning Electron Microscopy

The surface morphology of the pro-niosomes was evaluated by scanning electron microscopy. The proniosome gel was placed on a cavity glass slide and few water was added drop wise along the side of the cover slip. The formation of vesicles was monitored through a microscope and photomicrograph was taken.

Percentage Drug Entrapment

The PDE of Piroxicam NIOSOMES was calculated after determining the amount of untrapped drug by dialysis³⁸. The dialysis was performed by adding the niosomal dispersion to a dialysis tube (donor compartment) and then dipping the tube into a beaker containing 200 mL of PBS pH 7.4 with 0.05% SLS (receptor compartment) on a magnetic stirrer, rotated at a speed of 80 to 120 rpm for 3 hours. After 3 hours, the solution in the receptor compartment was

estimated for untrapped drug at 304 nm by using a UV spectrophotometer²⁷.

$$\text{Percent Entrapment} = \frac{\text{Total drug} - \text{Diffused drug}}{\text{totaldrug}} \times 100$$

In vitro diffusion study

In vitro dissolution study of proniosomal gel was performed by using franz diffusion cells by taking phosphate buffer 6.8 pH. The volume of diffusion medium used was 20 ml and maintained at a temperature of $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ with paddle speed set at 50 rpm throughout the experiment. An aliquot of 5 ml was collected at predetermined time intervals 30 min, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7 hrs respectively and replaced with fresh buffer to maintain constant volume⁴⁰. Samples

were analysed for Piroxicam using UV-Visible spectrophotometer at 304 nm.

Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy

Infrared spectra of pure drug, and optimized proniosomal formulation were obtained using FT-IR spectrophotometer (Bruker, Alpha-T, Lab India) by the conventional KBr pellet method¹³.

5. ANALYTICAL METHODS

5.1. Development of UV spectroscopic method

Preparation of calibration curve: The standard curve was prepared in the concentration range of 2–20 $\mu\text{l/ml}$. Different volumes of standard stock solutions, containing 2-20 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of drug were transferred to 10ml volumetric flasks and volume was made up with methanol. The absorbance was measured at 304 nm against the corresponding reagent blank. The drug concentrations of piroxicam were analyzed by UV-Spectrophotometer at 304 nm (fig. 2).

Fig.2:Standard graph of Piroxicam
Table 2:Standard graph of Piroxicam

conc(mg/ml)	abs
0	0
0.2	0.1307
0.4	0.2423
0.6	0.3502
0.8	0.4689
1	0.5801
1.2	0.6987

Table 3: Optical Parameters

Parameters (Units)	Values
	Piroxicam
λ max/ nm	304 nm
Linearity Range ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	0-1.2
Slope, <i>b</i>	0.5753X

FTIR:

The FTIR was performed for both pure drug and formulation, and the results clearly indicated that there is no incompatibility between pure drug and formulation.

Fig 3: pure drug-piroxicam

Fig 4: optimised formulation

Entrapment Efficiency:

Proniosomes have generated interest as a topical formulation and to achieve the desirable therapeutic effect of Niosomes as drug carriers, they must be loaded with sufficient amount of active compound. Proniosomes prepared with non-ionic surfactants of alkyl ester including Span (sorbitan esters) and Tween (polyoxyethylene sorbitan esters) were utilized to determine the encapsulation of associated Piroxicam and vesicle size. As shown in Table 6, encapsulation efficiency of proniosomes formed from formulation NG1, NG3, NG4, NG5 proniosome gel exhibit lower encapsulation efficiency when compared to NG2. The results of entrapment

efficiency are shown in the fig 3. Piroxicam was best encapsulated by niosomal gel prepared using Span 40 when compared to other grades and this was attributed to the fact that S40 is solid at room temperature, showed higher phase transition temperature and low permeability. The encapsulation efficiency of S40 at 59.50% was much higher than S20, T60 and T80 at 23.84%, 28.84%, 17.24% and 15.84%. Furthermore S40 was optimized based on the encapsulation efficiency by taking different ratios of surfactant and lecithin and encapsulation percentage is determined. Table 7 shows the effect of various ratios of sorbitan fatty acid esters and lecithin on the encapsulation of Piroxicam in niosomal gel.

Table 4: Encapsulation percentage of various Niosomal Gel Formulations

Sl. No	Niosomal code	Encapsulation percentage (%)
1.	NG1	23.84 ±1.4
2.	NG2	59.50 ±2.3
3.	NG3	23.84 ±1.6
4.	NG4	28.84 ±2.0
5.	NG5	17.24 ±1.9

Table 5: Niosomal gel formulations with various ratios of sorbitan fatty acid esters and lecithin:

Sl. No	Niosomal code	Ratios		Piroxicam (mg)	Cholesterol (mg)
		SPAN 40	Lecithin		
1.	NG1	1	1	10	20
2.	NG2	2	1	10	20
3.	NG3	1	2	10	20
4.	NG4	3	1	10	20
5	NG5	1	3	10	20

The encapsulation percentage obtained by different ratios of sorbitan fatty acid esters and lecithin were almost same with slight difference that is formulations having more of surfactant have encapsulation slightly higher than those with higher lecithin ratio. Table 8 shows the encapsulation percentage of different formulations. The encapsulations Percentage of different formulations of Span 40 are shown in the fig 4.

Table 6: Encapsulation percentage of different formulations

Sl. No	Niosomal code	Ratios		Encapsulation percentage (Percentage)
		SPAN 40	Lecithin	
1.	NG1	1	1	66±1.0
2.	NG2	2	1	65 ±1.9
3.	NG3	1	2	57.4 ±1.6
4.	NG4	3	1	61.2 ±2.1
	NG5	1	3	57.2 ±1.5

In-vitro Studies

Fig 5: In vitro drug release profile for Niosomal Gels

Table 7: Release kinetics of optimized formulations in in-vitro drug release

time (t)	root (t)	cumulative (%) release q	log (t)	log(%) release	log (%) remain	release rate (cumulative release / t)
0	0	0	0.000	0.000	2.000	0.000
1	1.000	22.89	0.000	1.360	1.887	22.890
2	1.414	39.17	0.301	1.593	1.784	19.585
3	1.732	55.3	0.477	1.743	1.650	18.433
4	2.000	62.64	0.602	1.797	1.572	15.660
5	2.236	70.05	0.699	1.845	1.476	14.010
6	2.449	77.92	0.778	1.892	1.344	12.987
7	2.646	89.5	0.845	1.952	1.021	12.786

RELEASE KINETICS:

The Release kinetics of the optimized formulations studied in in-vitro drug release are given in the tables

Different Kinetic model of the Formulations NG2, NG3, NG4 and NG5 are shown in the figure.

Thus it is evident from the study that NG4 formulation of Piroxicam niosomal gel showed good stability characteristics, prolonged release of entrapped Piroxicam with enhanced penetration and retention of drug in the skin facilitating local action

thus achieving the main objectives in the development of formulation for Therapy.

To ascertain the drug release mechanism and release rate data of the various formulations, the data's were model fitted by Drug Kinetic Models. The models selected were Zero order, First order, Higuchi Matrix, Weibull, Korsmeyer Peppas, Hixon-Crowell. The release pattern was found to be first Order and the best fit model was found to be higuchi order

Scanning Electron Microscopy:**CONCLUSION:**

Studies were conducted with various levels of amount of cholesterol and span 60 to optimize proniosomal. All formulations were evaluated for the different Physico-chemical characteristics. Formulated proniosomes gave satisfactory results for entrapment efficiency. *In Vitro* drug release behavior was improved. There is no significant difference between the FTIR patterns of the optimized formulation of proniosomal gel and to that of the pure drug.

REFERENCES

- 1) Aulton M, *Pharmaceutics. "The Science of Dosage Form Design"*. International student edition., published by Churchill Livingstone., 2002.PP.304-321.
- 2) Ansel H, Allen L & Jr. popovich N, "Ansel's Pharmaceutical Dosage Forms and Drug Delivery Systems, 8th edition, published by Lippincott Williams & Wilkins", 2004.PP.227-259.
- 3) Banker GS, *Modern pharmaceutics, 3rd edition*, Marcel Dekker Inc, Newyork., 2002.PP.576 – 820.
- 4) Rathore K. "A Review on Hydrotropes: Compounds for Solubility Enhancement of Poorly Water Soluble Substances". *The Pharma Review.*, 2007- 2008.
- 5) Indian Pharmacopoeia, Government of India ministry of health and family Welfare, 4th ed., 1996.The Controller of Publication, Delhi, 332.
- 6) Shinde A. "Solubilization of poorly soluble drugs". *A Review Pharmainfo.net.*, 2007.PP.4-7.
- 7) Liu R. Introduction, In: Liu, R., (Ed.), "Water-Insoluble Drug Formulation". 2nd ed., 2008, CRS press, New York, 1.
- 8) Brahmkar D.M. "Biopharmaceutics and Pharmacokinetics". 2009.PP. 349-357.
- 9) Alekhya Gurrapu, Raju, Sharan reddy, Swetha, Jyothi. "Improved oral delivery of valsartan from maltodextrin based proniosome powders". *Advanced Powder Technology.*, (2011).
- 10) Walve JR, Rane BR, Gujrathi NA, Bakaliwal SR, Pawar SP. "Proniosomes: A surrogated carrier for improved transdermal drug delivery system". *IJRAP.*, (2011).PP. 743-750.
- 11) Ankur Gupta, Sunil Kumar Prajapati, Balamurugan M, Mamta Singh and Daksh Bhatia (2007). "Design and Development of a Proniosomal Transdermal Drug Delivery System for Captopril". *Tropical J. Pharm Res.*,(2007).PP. 687-693.
- 12) Sudhamani. "Proniosomes – A Promising Drug Carriers". *Int. J. PharmTech Res.*,(2010).
- 13) Raja K*, Jestin Palu Ukken, Athul P V, Tamizharasi.S, Sivakumar.T. "Formulation and Evaluation maltodextrin based proniosomal drug delivery system containing anti-diabetic (Glipizide) drug". *International Journal of Pharm Tech Research.*,(2011).PP.471-477.
- 14) Chandra A and Sharma PK. "Proniosome based drug delivery system of piroxicam". *African J Pharm and Ph.cology.*, (2008). 2(9):PP.184-190.